

Biomechanical and Biological Aspects of Carbon Composites (SEPCARB® AND CERASEP®)

J. Thebault, B. Buttazzoni, J. J. Choury

Societe Europeenne de Propulsion, Boite Poste 37, 33165 Saint Medard en Jalles, Cedex, France

1 - INTRODUCTION

Chronologically carbon/carbon composites have been developed in SEP for space propulsion requirements. For this type of application are mainly used the thermal characteristics of carbons. Such materials constitute the first generation of C/C composites.

These materials evolved and others important applications appeared in which thermal but also mechanical properties are involved (strength, friction coefficient etc...). This type of materials constitute the second generation of C/C composites and aircraft discbrakes are a typical model of application. Meanwhile the biocompatibility of some carbons, particularly under the "glassy" and "pyrolytic L.T.I." forms, has been proved (1, 2). In the same time an important need of improved prosthetic materials became evident, because of long dated limits or weakness of the present prosthetic materials. In view of the above we looked for C/C as a solution for a number of problems in orthopaedic surgery. These problems are of two types :

- biomechanical
- biological (biocompatibility)

2 - BIOMECHANICAL ASPECTS

2.1 - Mechanical interaction between prosthesis and living tissue

A biomaterial is expected to stay in contact with a living tissue and to ensure a mechanical function. As a prosthesis, it will modify the mechanical stresses distribution into the nearer tissue. This tissue, to a certain extent, is able to modify itself for adjusting its own mechanical characteristics to the new stresses (Wolff's law - 1892). This mechanical adjustment of the tissue to the prosthesis will occur only if the new stress, induced by the prosthesis, will not stay too far of the stress which locally existed before. Then the tissue (bone for example - fig 1) is locally going to strengthen or to weaken itself, but still keeping its function.

On the other hand, if the stress is too strong, the bone will be destroyed (necrosis) and if the stress is too weak, it will loose a lot of its mechanical properties (for example becoming porous - osteoporosis).

Thus the bone could easily break during and accidental hit. This slow modification of the living tissue will later on have an influence on the stress distribution into the prosthesis itself, which then in turn may be in a critical mechanical situation (3) fig 1.

2.2 - Biomechanical improvement of the present prosthesis

First, in contrary to what generally occurs in mechanics, in the case of prosthesis it must be pointed out that the function and the shape are settled and it is the mechanical characteristics of the material which must be matched.

In order to improve the present products, it is necessary to have a better mechanical matching between the prosthesis and the receiving tissue. This could be explained by the isoelasticity concept (4) which involves the shape and the osseous tissue properties on one hand and the geometry and the material prosthesis properties on the other hand (fig 2). Consequently, except in very particular cases, the isoelastic prosthetic material does not have the same Young's modulus as the adjacent tissue's one. If the modulus of the prosthetic material is too low, this will lead to overloading areas either in the tissue or in the prosthesis. The involvement of isoelasticity, suitable to a large number of different prosthesis (hip, knee, bone plates, vascular grafts, dental implants, etc...) is that each type of prosthesis will be a specific case requiring a material with an adequate modulus and even locally variable. This necessity leads to composites materials because it is one of the main advantages of those to allow such a matching of mechanical properties.

2.3 - Carbon composites materials

Our experience in the field of composites materials, connected with the biocompatibility of some carbons, led us to envisage the use of C/C composites - Sepcarb[®] - for producing prosthesis with high performance characteristics. The study of different cases has shown that the isoelasticity concept led to materials with rather low Young's modulus ($E < 75$ GPa). These moduli are lower than those of the presently used materials (metal alloys $E \approx 220$ GPa) but higher than the bone's one ($E \approx 15$ GPa). This rather low modulus must be associated with high mechanical strength ($\sigma_F > 350$ MPa). On fig 3, showing the state of the art at the beginning of this study, one can see that there are no all carbon - composite materials able to fit the biomaterials requirements (5, 6).

This led us to develop a new generation of C/C composites - 3^d generation : structural Sepcarb - characterized by high mechanical properties (fig 4). In addition to their high mechanical resistance (fig 5) and their rather low modulus (fig 6) these materials have a good toughness and an excellent fatigue behaviour since we cannot notice any loss of the mechanical properties after 10^6 and even 10^7 flexural cycles under a stress of 80 % of the initial ultimate stress. The data given by acoustic emission (Kaiser's effect for example) corroborate that the material is undamaged by fatigue cycles. When only made of pure carbon, these materials are not sensitive to stress corrosion (as metals do), they are stable in time and do not release any removable compounds (as organic resins, such as PMMA cement, do).

2.4 - Application examples

2.4.1 - Hip joint prosthesis shaft

Structural Sepcarb hip joint prosthesis shafts have been made and tested mechanically (fig 7). The results obtained, quantitatively with shaft actually implanted, show that the C/C Procarb[®] prosthesis is obviously more flexible than the actual prosthesis (fig 8) and that this fact clearly leads to a more homogeneous stress distribution (fig 9) (7).

The resulting limited osseous remodelling should allow to use hip joint prosthesis in the case of younger people.

2.4.2 - Bone plates

We have also applied the isoelasticity concept to the production of structural C/C bone plates. The results of the mechanical tests (fig 10) show that the Osteocarb[®] bone plate is about 3.5 time more flexible than the metal one, and at the same time has an equal or even higher strength in the elastic behaviour domain. The expected isoelasticity results with bone plates have been confirmed by animal implantation. In fact, after 3 month, the calus obtained is stiffer, the underlying bone is less porous and the fracture healing apparently is obtained quicker than with the metal plate. So bone plates made with structural Sepcarb should reduce the number of iterative fractures.

2.5 - Carbon ceramised composites

For the realization of articular surfaces (hip and knee joint prosthesis) we need materials having low friction coefficient and low wear, in addition to high mechanical strength.

For this need we have produced carbon composites, in wich all, or a part of, the matrix is made with ceramic (Cerasesp[®]). We have choosed silicon carbide obtained by chemical vapour infiltration (CVI) (8).

These materials have very high mechanical properties (fig 5, 6) and a very good fatigue behaviour. Preliminary results of the tribological and wear tests are very encouraging.

3 - BIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CARBON COMPOSITES

3.1 - Biocompatibility of Sepcarb[®] and Cerasesp[®] materials

The biocompatibility of carbon is generally well established, it seems that some differences are affected by the origin of fibers (precursor) and by the process of manufacturing the material. The biocompatibility of some type of carbons, like "vitreous" carbon, "pyrolytic LTI" carbon and PAN precursor carbon fiber have reached a time life up to ten years of implantation (1, 2, 9).

On our part, we have undertaken in vitro and in vivo tests of biocompatibility, both with bulk and powder materials, that have guided to choose PAN precursor carbon fiber and anisotropic pyrotytic carbon matrix made by a CVI process in order to obtain the best biocompatible all carbon composite material (10).

In a same way, we have demonstrated the biological inertia of carbon - ceramic composite with SiC made by a CVI process.

To improve the bonding between osseous tissue and implant without a fibrous layer, we can deposit by a chemical spray process a thin coating of hydroxyapatite product (11).

The effect when implanted is to seal quickly the prosthesis without use of acrylic cement.

3.2 - Application examples

After a one year duration of implantation in sheep, the carbon/carbon Osteocarb[®] plate shows the growing of osseous tissue into the porous structure of the material. This confirms the ability of these composites to form orthopaedic devices implantable without cement (fig 12).

In the field of hemocompatibility, after insertion into dogs of intra atrial implants made with carbon/carbon Hemocarb[®] composites we noticed two month later the presence of a neovascular tissue with stabilized endothelial - like cell lining (fig 13).

The use of carbon fibers to repair tendons and ligaments is well established now (9). The implantation of quasi elastic braided C/C Biocarb[®] reinforcement into the knee of dogs gives a neoligament growing around the fibers with a minimum dispersion of particles. In clinical applications good results after two years are observed with repairs of knee lateral ligament and Achille tendon.

For reinforcement of cutaneous and gristly organs, veterinary applications have begun one year ago with ear straightenings and perineal repairs of dogs (fig 14).

Dental implants with cylindrical or conical shape made of structural C/C composites are in experimental phase with both animal and clinical implantations. The first results are incentives.

4 - CONCLUSION

With the aim to improve the present prosthesis, biomechanical considerations lead us to define specific characteristics of prosthetic materials, like high strength, moderate Young's modulus, and good fatigue behaviour.

Composites materials are the only ones to be able to fullfill simultaneously all these characteristics.

If we consider that carbon is one of the best biocompatible material, the carbon/carbon composites are particularly well adapted to built prosthesis.

We have shown that it is possible to obtain this type of C/C composites with high structural behaviour and good biocompatibility.

Their properties may be adapted to the tribological needs of articular prosthesis by local ceramic reinforcement with SiC matrix, and to the natural sealing of the implants by an apatitic chemical spray process.

The results of implantation confirms the interest shown by these materials from which new designs of prosthesis are possibles.

These 3^d generation materials, initially studied for biomedical applications, due to their high mechanical and thermal properties and their chemical inertness, open the way to many other applications.

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Fig. 1

- 1 - overloading : the bone die
- 2 - underloading :
the bone weaken
- 3 - debonding and breaking
of the prosthesis.

HIP JOINT PROSTHESIS

3 Cases

The optimal modulus of a prosthesis material has not to be necessarily the same as for the bone

Fig. 2

Fig. 3 - strength and modulus range of C/C composites with different fibre arrangements (5).

Fig. 4

Fig. 7

Fig. 6

Fig. 5

Fig. 8

Stresses on Implanted Prosthesis F = 150 daN

Fig. 9

Flexural test (3points)

Fig. 10

Fig. 11 hydroxyapatite coating
(x150).

Fig. 12 - bone ingrowth into the C/C

Fig. 13 intra atrial implantation

Fig. 14 dogs's ear implantation

